

Toxic effects of latex of *Croton tiglium* on *Lymnaea acuminata* and *Channa punctatus*

Efectos tóxicos del latex de *Croton tiglium* sobre *Lymnaea acuminata* y *Channa punctatus*

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ABSTRACT

The aqueous latex extracts of *Croton tiglium* Linn. plant belonging to family Euphorbiaceae, was found to have strong molluscicidal activity against freshwater snail *Lymnaea (Radix) acuminata* Lamarck. Exposure of sub-lethal doses of latex extracts of this plant on snail *Lymnaea (Radix) acuminata* Lamarck over 24h or 96h caused significant change in carbohydrates and nitrogenous metabolism in nervous, hepatopancreas and ovotestis tissue.

Non-target fish *Channa punctatus* (Bloch) (Channidae [Ophicephalidae]) (which shares the habitat with these snails) was also exposed to sub-lethal doses for 96h exposure periods for measuring its potential, the environmental toxicity (if any). Sub-lethal exposure of fish shows significant alteration in carbohydrate and nitrogenous metabolism in muscle, liver and gonadal tissues. Withdrawal study also shows that there is a partial recovery in snail's tissues but nearly complete recovery in fish tissues after 7th day of the withdrawal of treatment, which supports the view that plant products are safer in use as molluscicides than synthetic pesticides.

RESUMEN

Los extractos acuosos del latex de *Croton tiglium* Linn., de la familia Euphorbiaceae, tienen fuertes efectos molusquicidas sobre *Lymnaea (Radix) acuminata* Lamarck. La exposición a dosis subletales de dicho latex durante 24 o 96 horas produjo un significativo cambio en el metabolismo de los carbohidratos y del nitrógeno en el tejido nervioso, hepatopáncreas y ovotestis.

El pez *Channa punctatus* (Bloch) (Channidae [Ophicephalidae]) (que comparte hábitat con estos moluscos) también se expuso a dosis subletales durante el mismo periodo, con el fin de comprobar el potencial tóxico del extracto. Dicha exposición mostró una alteración significativa del metabolismo de carbohidratos y nitrógeno en los tejidos muscular, hepático y gonadal. También se comprobó que existe una recuperación parcial en los tejidos del molusco y una casi total recuperación en los del pez tras el séptimo día después de abandonado el tratamiento, lo que apoya la visión de que los productos procedentes de plantas son más seguros como molusquicidas que los pesticidas sintéticos.

KEY WORDS: *Channa punctatus*, *Croton tiglium*, metabolism, *Lymnaea acuminata*.

PALABRAS CLAVE: *Channa punctatus*, *Croton tiglium*, metabolismo, *Lymnaea acuminata*.

INTRODUCTION

Snails of the genus *Lymnaea* (*Radix*) and *Indoplanorbis* Deshayes are the hosts in the life cycle of the liver fluke (genus *Fasciola* Cobbold), which is responsible for fascioliasis, a disease affecting cattle and live stock population of Northern part of India (SINGH AND AGARWAL, 1981). Control of harmful freshwater snails through synthetic pesticides has been reviewed in detail by various workers (AGARWAL AND SINGH, 1988; SINGH AND AGARWAL, 1990, 1993, 1995; SINGH, SINGH, MISHRA AND AGARWAL, 1996). With growing awareness of environmental pollution caused by synthetic molluscicides (RITCHIE, 1973; CHRISTIE, PRENTICE, UPATHAM AND BANISH, 1978; CARDARELLI, 1974; DUNCAN, 1974; SRIVASTAVA AND SINGH, 2001), efforts are being made to find out molluscicides of plant origin. Being the product of biosynthesis, they are highly toxic and easily biodegradable in environment (MARSTON AND HOSTETTMAN, 1987; SINGH AND AGARWAL, 1992, 1993; SINGH ET AL., 1996). Earlier studies indicate that the Euphorbiales have potent molluscicidal activity against the freshwater snails *Lymnaea* (*Radix*) *acuminata* Lamarck and *Indoplanorbis exustus* Deshayes (SINGH AND AGARWAL, 1988, 1990, 1992, 1995; YADAV AND SINGH, 2001). But little work has been done on their mode of action and their environmental impact on non-target organism.

The aim of this study is to measure the effects of sub-lethal exposure to aqueous extracts of latex of *Croton tiglium* Linn. on different biochemical parameters of freshwater target snail *Lymnaea* (*Radix*) *acuminata* Lamarck and non-target fish *Channa punctatus* (Bloch) (Channidae [Ophicephalidae]). *Channa punctatus* is a freshwater common fish of Indian captured fishery and share the habitat with the snail *Lymnaea acuminata*.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Latex of *Croton tiglium* Linn. (Family Euphorbiaceae) plant was collected

from Botanical garden of D.D.U, Gorakhpur University Gorakhpur India. White latex produced by this plant was drained in to glass beakers by cutting the stem apices and lyophilised at -40°C and the lyophilized dry powder was used for further study. The wet weight of 1 ml latex was 800 mg and dry weight (Lyophilised at -40°C) was 300 mg.

Adult *Lymnaea acuminata* (2.6 ± 0.3 cm in shell height) and freshwater fish *Channa punctatus* (10.5 ± 0.9 cm in length) were collected from Ramgarh Lake of Gorakhpur district, and maintained in plastic tank for acclimatization to laboratory conditions. The acclimatized animals were treated with latex of *Croton tiglium* Linn. according to the method of SINGH AND AGARWAL (1988). The experimental animals were treated with sub-lethal doses (40% and 80% of LC_{50}) of the latices of *Croton tiglium* Linn. for 24h or 96h exposure periods. Six aquaria were set up for each dose and each aquarium contained either 30 snails or 10 fishes in 6L dechlorinated tap water.

The LC_{50} of aqueous latex extracts of *Croton tiglium* Linn. against snail *Lymnaea acuminata* was 0.060 mg/L and 0.014 mg/L for 24h and 96h, respectively (YADAV AND SINGH, 2001).

After completion of treatment the test animals were removed from the aquaria and washed with water. The nervous, hepatopancreas and ovotestis of *Lymnaea acuminata* and muscle, liver and gonadal tissue of *Channa punctatus* were excised and used for biochemical analysis. Control animals were held in similar conditions without any treatment.

In order to see the effect of withdrawal from treatment, the snails were first exposed to 80% of LC_{50} for 96h exposure periods and fishes were treated with 80% of LC_{50} (24h) for 96h exposure periods, following which snails and fishes were transfer to latex free water. This water was changed every 24h for the next seven days, after which biochemical parameters were estimated in different tissues. Each experiment was replicated at least six times and the values have been expressed as mean \pm SE of six replicates. Student's 't' test

and analysis of variance were applied to locate significant changes (SOKAL AND ROHLF, 1973).

BIOCHEMICAL ESTIMATIONS

Protein: Protein levels were estimated according to the method of LOWRY, ROSENBOUGH, FARR AND RANDALL (1951) using bovine serum albumin as standard. Homogenates (5mg/ml, w/v) were prepared in 10%TCA.

Total free amino acids: Estimation of total free amino acid was made according to the method of SPICES (1957). Homogenates (10mg/ml, w/v) were prepared in 95% ethanol, centrifuged at 6000 xg and used for amino acid estimation.

Nucleic acids: Estimation of DNA and RNA was performed, by methods of SCHNEIDER (1957) using diphenylamine and orcinol reagents, respectively. Homogenates (1 mg/ml, w/v) were prepared in 5% TCA at 90°C, centrifuged at 5000 g for 20 min and supernatant was prepared used for estimation. Both DNA and RNA have been expressed as mg/mg tissue.

Glycogen: Glycogen was estimated by the Anthrone method of VAN DER VIES (1954) as modified by MAHENDRU AND AGARWAL (1982) for snails. In present experiment 50 mg of tissue was homogenised with 5ml of cold 5%TCA. The homogenate were filtered and 1.0 ml of filtrate was used for assay.

Pyruvate: Pyruvate level was measured according to FRIEDEMANN AND HAUGEN (1943). Homogenate (50 mg/ml, w/v) was prepared in 10% TCA. Sodium pyruvate was taken as standard.

Lactate: Lactate was estimated according to BARKER AND SUMMERSON (1941), modified by HUCKABEE (1961). Homogenate (50 mg/ml, w/v) was prepared in 10% cold TCA. Sodium lactate was taken as standard.

Protease: Protease activity was estimated by the method of MOORE AND STEIN (1954). Homogenate (50 mg/ml, w/v) was prepared in cold distilled

water. Optical density was measured at 570 nm. The enzyme activity was expressed in μmol of tyrosine equivalent/mg protein/h.

Acid and alkaline phosphatase: Activities of acid and alkaline phosphatase were measured by the method of BERGMAYER (1967) and modified by SINGH AND AGARWAL, (1983). Tissue homogenate (2% w/v) were prepared in ice cold 0.9% saline and centrifuged at 5000xg at 0°C for 15 min. Optical density was measured at 420 nm against a blank, prepared simultaneously. The enzyme activity has been expressed as amount of p-nitrophenol formed/30min/mg protein in supernatant.

Lactic dehydrogenase: Lactic dehydrogenase (LDH) activity was measured according to the method of ANONYMOUS (1984). Homogenates (50 mg/ml, w/v) were prepared in 1 ml of 0.1 M phosphate buffer, pH 7.5 for 5 min in an ice bath. Enzyme activity has been expressed as nanomol of pyruvate reduced/min/mg protein.

Succinic dehydrogenase: Succinic dehydrogenase activity was measured by the method of ARRIGONI AND SINGER (1962). Homogenate (50 mg/ml, w/v) was prepared in 1 ml of 0.5M potassium phosphate buffer, pH 7.6 for 5 min in an ice bath. Optical density was measured at 600nm. Enzyme activity has been expressed as μmol dye reduced/min/mg protein.

Cytochrome oxidase: Cytochrome oxidase activity was measured according to the method of COOPERSTEIN AND LAZAROW (1951). Homogenates (50 mg/ml, w/v) were prepared in 1 ml of 0.33 M phosphate buffer (pH 7.4) for 5 min in ice bath. Enzyme activity has been expressed in arbitrary units/min/mg of proteins.

Acetylcholinesterase: Acetylcholinesterase was estimated by the method of ELLMAN, COURTNEY, ANDRES AND FEATHERSTONE., (1961) as adapted by SINGH AND AGARWAL (1982) for snail tissue. Homogenates (50 mg/ml, w/v) were prepared in 0.1 M phosphate buffer in ice bath. Optical density was measured at 412 nm at 25°C. Enzyme activity

expressed in μmol 'SH' hydrolysed/min/mg protein.

RESULTS

Effect on freshwater target snail:

Data of sub-lethal (40% and 80% of LC_{50}) exposure of freshwater snail *Lymnaea acuminata* against aqueous extracts of latex of *Croton tiglium* are given in Table I-IV. Exposure of snails to 40% and 80% of LC_{50} of aqueous extracts of latex of *Croton tiglium* for 24h or 96h caused significant alterations in nitrogenous and carbohydrate metabolism in different tissues of the freshwater snail *Lymnaea acuminata*.

Effects on nitrogenous metabolism:

Total protein and nucleic acids (DNA and RNA) levels were significantly reduced, while free amino acid level was significantly enhanced after the exposure to sub-lethal doses in all the body tissues. Acid and alkaline phosphatase activities were significantly reduced, while protease activity was increased after the exposure.

Total protein levels were reduced to 39%, 45% and 36% of controls after exposure to 80% of LC_{50} (96h) of aqueous latex extracts respectively in the nervous, hepatopancreas and ovotestis tissue of *Lymnaea acuminata*, respectively. DNA level was reduced to 36%, 45% and 28% of controls after treatment with 80% of LC_{50} (96h) of aqueous latex extracts in nervous, hepatopancreas and ovotestis, respectively. RNA level was reduced to 42%, 48% and 34% of controls after treatment with 80% of LC_{50} (96h) of aqueous latex extracts respectively in nervous, hepatopancreas and ovotestis of snail. Total free amino acid levels were induced to 167%, 140% and 170% of controls after treatment with 80% of LC_{50} (96h) of aqueous latex extracts respectively in nervous, hepatopancreas and ovotestis of snail (Table II).

Activity of acid phosphatase was inhibited to 38%, 67% and 58% of controls after treatment with 80% of LC_{50} (96h) of aqueous latex extracts respecti-

vely in nervous, hepatopancreas and ovotestis. Activity of alkaline phosphatase was reduced to 30%, 35% and 32% of controls after treatment with 80% of LC_{50} (96h) of aqueous latex extracts respectively in nervous, hepatopancreas and ovotestis. Protease activity was increased to 136%, 130% and 132% of controls after treatment with 80% of LC_{50} (96h) of aqueous latex extracts respectively in the nervous, hepatopancreas and ovotestis of snail *Lymnaea acuminata* (Table II).

Effects on carbohydrate metabo-

lism: Glycogen and pyruvate levels were significantly reduced, while lactate level was significantly enhanced after the exposure to sub-lethal doses in all the body tissues. Lactic dehydrogenase (LDH), cytochrome oxidase and acetylcholinesterase (AChE) activities were significantly reduced, while succinic dehydrogenase (SDH) activity was increased after the exposure.

Glycogen level was reduced to 27%, 40% and 26% of controls after treatment with 80% of LC_{50} (96h) of aqueous latex extracts respectively in nervous, hepatopancreas and ovotestis. Pyruvate level was reduced to 37%, 44% and 39% of controls after treatment with 80% of LC_{50} (96h) of aqueous latex extracts respectively in nervous, hepatopancreas and ovotestis tissue. Lactate level was increased to 175%, 182% and 172% of controls after treatment with 80% of LC_{50} (96h) of aqueous latex extracts respectively in nervous, hepatopancreas and ovotestis (Table IV).

LDH activity was reduced to 26%, 33% and 28% of controls after treatment with 80% of LC_{50} (96h) of aqueous latex extracts respectively in nervous, hepatopancreas and ovotestis tissue. Activity of cytochrome oxidase was reduced to 39%, 43% and 40% of controls after treatment with 80% of LC_{50} (96h) of aqueous latex extracts respectively in nervous, hepatopancreas and ovotestis. AChE activity was reduced to 26%, 22% and 27% of controls after treatment with 80% of LC_{50} (96h) of aqueous latex extracts respectively in nervous, hepatopancreas and ovotestis of snail. SDH

Table I. Changes in total protein, total free amino acids, nucleic acid (DNA and RNA) (mg/mg) level and activity of protease (μmol of tyrosine equivalents/mg protein/h) and acid and alkaline phosphatase (μmol substrate hydrolysed/30 min/mg protein) in Nervous (NT), Hepatopancreas (HP) and Ovary (OT) tissues of *Lymnaea acuminata* after exposure to 40% and 80% of LC₅₀ of aqueous latex extracts of *Croton tiglium* after 24h.

Tabla I. Cambios en los niveles de proteínas totales, aminoácidos libres, ácidos nucleicos (DNA y RNA) (mg/mg) y en la actividad proteasa (μmol de equivalentes de tirosina/mg de proteína/h) y fosfatasas ácida y alcalina (μmol sustrato hidrolizado/30 min/mg proteína) en tejido nervioso (NT), hepatopáncreas (HP) y ovotestis (OT) de *Lymnaea acuminata* tras exposición a LC₅₀ de extracto acuoso de latex de *Croton tiglium* al 40 y al 80% después de 24 horas.

	Tissues	Control	40% of LC ₅₀ (24h) (0.024mg,DW/L)	80% of LC ₅₀ (24h) (0.048mg,DW/L)
Protein	NT	68.0±0.28 (100)	37.8±0.33* (55)	27.8±0.33* (40)
	HP	70.1±0.52 (100)	47.8±0.33* (68)	37.1±0.33* (52)
	OT	72.44±0.80 (100)	39.11±0.70* (54)	27.52±0.84* (38)
Amino acid	NT	34.3±0.36 (100)	49.5±0.22* (129)	48.6±0.36* (141)
	HP	28.8±0.33 (100)	36.6±0.92* (127)	39.1±0.33* (135)
	OT	36.4±0.46 (100)	48.05±0.58* (132)	52.78±0.65* (145)
DNA	NT	72.44±0.80 (100)	57.95±0.80* (80)	50.70±0.70* (70)
	HP	70.11±0.52 (100)	61.68±0.65* (88)	52.58±0.48* (75)
	OT	75.66±0.80 (100)	56.33±0.40* (74)	51.0±0.37* (67)
RNA	NT	62.01±0.28 (100)	52.08±0.35* (84)	40.30±0.40* (65)
	HP	60.10±0.52 (100)	52.89±0.50* (88)	42.07±0.52* (70)
	OT	65.33±0.88 (100)	53.83±0.44* (82)	46.66±0.46* (68)
Protease	NT	0.321±0.056 (100)	0.375±0.057* (117)	0.417±0.048* (130)
	HP	0.342±0.064 (100)	0.393±0.056* (115)	0.427±0.067* (125)
	OT	0.345±0.058 (100)	0.407±0.056* (118)	0.448±0.047* (130)
Acid phosphatase	NT	0.191±0.0004 (100)	0.158±0.0006* (83)	0.120±0.007* (63)
	HP	0.185±0.0006 (100)	0.160±0.0004* (87)	0.129±0.0006* (70)
	OT	0.190±0.0008 (100)	0.161±0.0005* (85)	0.123±0.0004* (65)
Alkaline phosphatase	NT	0.390±0.0004 (100)	0.327±0.0005* (84)	0.261±0.0008* (67)
	HP	0.345±0.0006 (100)	0.303±0.0005* (88)	0.245±0.0006* (71)
	OT	0.385±0.0004 (100)	0.327±0.0008* (85)	0.261±0.0007* (68)

*, Significant (P<0.05) Student's 't' test was applied between control and treated groups. Values are mean ±SE of six replicates. Values in parenthesis are percent change with control taken as 100%.

activity was increased to 175%, 168% and 173% of controls after treatment with 80% of LC₅₀ (96h) of aqueous latex extracts respectively in nervous, hepatopancreas and ovotestis tissue (Table IV).

Effect on freshwater non-target fish: Higher doses (LC₉₀ of snails) have

no apparent toxic effect on freshwater fish *Channa punctatus* after 24h exposure. But exposure of fishes to sub-lethal doses (i.e. 40% and 80% of 24h LC₅₀ of snail) of aqueous extracts of latex of *Croton tiglium* for 96h caused a significant alteration in nitrogenous and carbohydrates metabolism in different

Table II. Changes in total protein, total free amino acids, nucleic acid (DNA and RNA) (mg/mg) level and activity of protease (μmol of tyrosine equivalents/mg protein/h) and acid and alkaline phosphatase (μmol substrate hydrolysed/30 min/mg protein) in Nervous (NT), Hepatopancreas (HP) and Ovary (OT) tissues of snail *Lymnaea acuminata* after 96h exposure to 40% and 80% of LC₅₀ of aqueous latex extracts of *Croton tiglium* and 7th days after withdrawal.

Tabla II. Cambios en los niveles de proteínas totales, aminoácidos libres, ácidos nucleicos (DNA y RNA) (mg/mg) y en la actividad proteasa (μmol de equivalentes de tirosina/mg de proteína/h) y fosfatasas ácida y alcalina (μmol sustrato hidrolizado/30 min/mg proteína) en tejido nervioso (NT), hepatopáncreas (HP) y ovotestis (OT) de *Lymnaea acuminata* tras exposición a LC₅₀ de extracto acuoso de latex de *Croton tiglium* al 40 y al 80% después de 96 horas y 7 días después de la prueba.

	Tissues	Control	40% of LC ₅₀ (96h) (0.006mg,DW/L)	80% of LC ₅₀ (96h) (0.012mg,DW/L)	7 th day after withdrawal
Protein	NT	68.0±0.28 (100)	36.8±0.33* (56)	26.6±0.36* (39)	61.8±0.24= (91)
	HP	70.1±0.52 (100)	38.1±0.33* (55)	31.0±0.49* (45)	67.9±0.07= (97)
	OT	73.33±0.83 (100)	38.1±0.33* (52)	26.9±0.34* (36)	69.6±0.41= (95)
Amino acid	NT	34.3±0.36 (100)	54.3±0.36* (159)	57.6±0.36* (167)	37.0±0.04= (108)
	HP	28.8±0.33 (100)	38.5±0.24* (134)	40.5±0.24* (140)	29.9±0.22= (104)
	OT	37.33±0.83 (100)	60.4±0.25* (162)	63.4±0.25* (170)	40.6±0.34= (109)
DNA	NT	72.66±0.83 (100)	39.96±0.33* (55)	26.15±0.37* (36)	71.93±0.84= (99)
	HP	72.83±1.11 (100)	47.33±0.16* (65)	32.77±0.38* (45)	71.38±1.12= (98)
	OT	75.66±0.80 (100)	37.01±0.40* (49)	21.01±0.40* (28)	68.09±0.71= (90)
RNA	NT	62.66±1.00 (100)	36.34±0.23* (58)	26.31±0.37* (42)	60.78±0.98= (97)
	HP	60.33±0.83 (100)	40.47±0.33* (67)	28.95±0.41* (48)	59.72±0.78= (99)
	OT	65.33±0.88 (100)	32.66±0.54* (50)	22.16±1.11* (34)	60.10±0.81= (92)
Protease	NT	0.344±0.06 (100)	0.409±0.06* (119)	0.382±0.01* (136)	0.330±0.046= (96)
	HP	0.365±0.03 (100)	0.423±0.03* (116)	0.474±0.03* (130)	0.346±0.062= (95)
	OT	0.369±0.01 (100)	0.435±0.01* (118)	0.487±0.01* (132)	0.361±0.028= (98)
Acid phosphatase	NT	0.194±0.009 (100)	0.0911±0.009* (47)	0.0737±0.007* (38)	0.177±0.0007= (91)
	HP	0.190±0.001 (100)	0.096±0.007* (51)	0.127±0.008* (67)	0.174±0.0009= (92)
	OT	0.188±0.002 (100)	0.082±0.002* (44)	0.109±0.001* (58)	0.175±0.0005= (93)
Alkaline phosphatase	NT	0.398±0.002 (100)	0.147±0.003* (37)	0.119±0.001* (30)	0.358±0.0018= (90)
	HP	0.361±0.003 (100)	0.151±0.002* (42)	0.126±0.006* (35)	0.336±0.0012= (93)
	OT	0.392±0.002 (100)	0.152±0.001* (39)	0.125±0.002* (32)	0.372±0.0013= (95)

=, Significant (P<0.05) when student's 't' test was applied between 80% of LC₅₀ (96h) and withdrawal groups
Details are as given in Table I.

body tissues of fish *Channa punctatus* (Tables V and VI).

Effects on nitrogenous metabolism:

Total protein and nucleic acids (DNA and RNA) levels were significantly reduced, while free amino acid level was significantly enhanced after the exposure to sub-

lethal doses in all the studied body tissues. Acid and alkaline phosphatase activities were significantly reduced, while protease activity was increased after the exposure.

Total protein levels were reduced to 78%, 75% and 68% and DNA level was reduced to 72%, 77% and 74% and RNA level was reduced to 67%, 72% and 70%

Table III. Changes in glycogen (mg/g), pyruvate ($\mu\text{mol/g}$), lactate (mg/g) level and activity of LDH ($\mu\text{mol/mg protein/h}$), SDH ($\mu\text{mol of dye reduced/min/mg protein}$), cytochrome oxidase (arbitrary unit/min/mg protein) and AChE ($\mu\text{mol 'SH' hydrolysed/min/mg protein}$) after 24h exposure to 40% and 80% of LC₅₀ of aqueous latex extracts of *Croton tiglium* in Nervous (NT), Hepatopancreas (HP) and Ovary (OT) tissues of snail *Lymnaea acuminata*.

Tabla III. Cambios en los niveles de glucógeno (mg/g), piruvato ($\mu\text{mol/g}$), lactato (mg/g), actividades de LDH ($\mu\text{mol/mg proteína/h}$), SDH ($\mu\text{mol de colorante reducido/min/mg proteína}$), citocromo oxidasa (unidad arbitraria/min/mg proteína) y AChE ($\mu\text{mol SH hidrolizado/min/mg proteína}$) en tejido nervioso (NT), hepatopáncreas (HP) y ovotestis (OT) de *Lymnaea acuminata* tras exposición a LC₅₀ de extracto acuoso de latex de *Croton tiglium* al 40 y al 80% durante 24 horas.

	Tissues	Control	40% of LC ₅₀ (24h) (0.024mg,DW/L)	80% of LC ₅₀ (24h) (0.048mg,DW/L)
Glycogen	NT	7.9±0.03 (100)	4.2±0.02* (53)	2.8±0.04* (35)
	HP	7.3±0.01 (100)	4.5±0.03* (61)	3.2±0.06* (43)
	OT	8.2±0.05 (100)	4.2±0.02* (52)	2.7±0.03* (34)
Pyruvate	NT	0.698±0.03 (100)	0.391±0.24* (56)	0.276±0.23* (39)
	HP	0.652±0.01 (100)	0.430±0.27* (66)	0.319±0.11* (49)
	OT	0.686±0.04 (100)	0.370±0.18* (54)	0.253±0.27* (37)
Lactate	NT	2.18±0.07 (100)	3.01±0.15* (138)	3.72±0.19* (170)
	HP	2.38±0.05 (100)	3.54±0.06* (149)	4.21±0.02* (177)
	OT	2.14±0.07 (100)	2.19±0.08* (136)	3.57±0.06* (167)
LDH	NT	0.073±0.006 (100)	0.047±0.006* (65)	0.029±0.002* (40)
	HP	0.067±0.001 (100)	0.046±0.003* (69)	0.031±0.002* (47)
	OT	0.072±0.001 (100)	0.048±0.004* (67)	0.027±0.001* (38)
SDH	NT	43.15±0.30 (100)	53.50±0.25* (124)	69.90±0.31* (162)
	HP	40.16±0.26 (100)	51.40±0.29* (128)	62.24±0.27* (155)
	OT	46.11±0.33 (100)	56.25±0.30* (122)	73.31±0.34* (159)
Cytochrome oxidase	NT	16.51±0.12 (100)	10.07±0.16* (61)	8.42±0.18* (51)
	HP	14.59±0.14 (100)	9.48±0.21* (65)	8.46±0.31* (58)
	OT	15.12±0.16 (100)	9.52±0.15* (63)	8.01±0.27* (53)
AChE	NT	0.072±0.0008 (100)	0.048±0.0003* (67)	0.032±0.0003* (45)
	HP	0.092±0.0002 (100)	0.065±0.0007* (71)	0.045±0.0002* (49)
	OT	0.070±0.0002 (100)	0.047±0.0003* (68)	0.032±0.0004* (46)

Details are as given in Table I.

in muscle, liver and gonadal tissue of fresh-water fish *Channa punctatus*. Total free amino acid levels were induced to 119%, 125% and 143% of controls after 96h treatment with 80% of LC₅₀ of aqueous latex extracts in muscle, liver and gonadal tissues, respectively (Table V).

Activity of acid phosphatase was inhibited to 30%, 37% and 32%. Activity of alkaline phosphatase was reduced to

38%, 40% and 37% and Protease activity was increased to 138%, 128% and 120% of controls after 96h treatment with 80% of LC₅₀ (96h) of aqueous latex extracts in muscle, liver and gonadal tissues, respectively (Table V).

Effects on carbohydrate metabolism: Glycogen and pyruvate levels were significantly reduced, while lactate

Table IV. Changes in glycogen (mg/g), pyruvate ($\mu\text{mol/g}$), lactate (mg/g) level and activity of LDH ($\mu\text{mol/mg protein/h}$), SDH ($\mu\text{mol of dye reduced/min/mg protein}$), cytochrome oxidase (arbitrary unit/min/mg protein) and AChE ($\mu\text{mol 'SH' hydrolysed/min/mg protein}$) after 96h exposure to 40% and 80% of LC_{50} of aqueous latex extracts of *Croton tiglium* in Nervous (NT), Hepatopancreas (HP) and Ovary (OT) tissues of snail *Lymnaea acuminata* and 7th day after withdrawal.

Tabla IV. Cambios en los niveles de glucógeno (mg/g), piruvato ($\mu\text{mol/g}$), lactato (mg/g), actividades de LDH ($\mu\text{mol/mg proteína/h}$), SDH ($\mu\text{mol de colorante reducido/min/mg proteína}$), citocromo oxidasa (unidad arbitraria/min/mg proteína) y AChE ($\mu\text{mol SH hidrolizado/min/mg proteína}$) en tejido nervioso (NT), hepatopáncreas (HP) y ovotestis (OT) de *Lymnaea acuminata* tras exposición a LC_{50} de extracto acuoso de latex de *Croton tiglium* al 40 y al 80% durante 96 horas y 7 días después de la prueba.

	Tissues	Control	40% of LC_{50} (96h) (0.006mg,DW/L)	80% of LC_{50} (96h) (0.012mg,DW/L)	7 th day after withdrawal
Glycogen	NT	7.9±0.03 (100)	3.6±0.17* (46)	2.1±0.06* (27)	7.3±0.03 ⁼ (93)
	HP	7.3±0.01 (100)	4.1±0.12* (57)	2.9±0.04* (40)	6.8±0.02 ⁼ (94)
	OT	7.8±0.03 (100)	3.5±0.17* (45)	2.02±0.06* (26)	7.3±0.04 ⁼ (93)
Pyruvate	NT	0.698±0.03 (100)	0.391±0.02* (56)	0.261±0.04* (37)	0.635±0.27 ⁼ (91)
	HP	0.657±0.02 (100)	0.407±0.08* (62)	0.289±0.07* (44)	0.592±0.08 ⁼ (90)
	OT	0.682±0.03 (100)	0.395±0.02* (58)	0.265±0.13* (39)	0.628±0.03 ⁼ (92)
Lactate	NT	2.18±0.07 (100)	3.08±0.17* (131)	3.92±0.16* (175)	2.46±0.04 ⁼ (113)
	HP	2.41±0.04 (100)	3.42±0.03* (142)	4.38±0.12* (182)	2.83±0.05 ⁼ (118)
	OT	2.17±0.07 (100)	2.79±0.08* (129)	3.73±0.03* (172)	2.46±0.03 ⁼ (113)
LDH	NT	0.073±0.006 (100)	0.032±0.003* (44)	0.019±0.002* (26)	0.065±0.003 ⁼ (90)
	HP	0.075±0.006 (100)	0.036±0.005* (48)	0.024±0.001* (33)	0.068±0.004 ⁼ (91)
	OT	0.076±0.003 (100)	0.034±0.003* (46)	0.021±0.001* (28)	0.070±0.003 ⁼ (90)
SDH	NT	16.41±0.18 (100)	23.63±0.17* (144)	28.7±0.07* (175)	18.38±0.84 ⁼ (112)
	HP	14.48±0.16 (100)	21.43±0.19* (148)	24.32±0.06* (168)	15.63±0.18 ⁼ (108)
	OT	18.41±0.07 (100)	26.14±0.08* (112)	31.84±0.17* (173)	20.43±0.20 ⁼ (111)
Cytochrome oxidase	NT	18.13±0.06 (100)	9.24±0.03* (51)	7.07±0.12* (39)	16.68±0.04 ⁼ (92)
	HP	14.50±0.15 (100)	7.97±0.12* (55)	6.23±0.03* (43)	13.05±0.12 ⁼ (90)
	OT	17.23±0.03 (100)	8.95±0.03* (52)	6.89±0.05* (40)	16.18±0.02 ⁼ (94)
AChE	NT	0.072±0.008 (100)	0.028±0.003* (39)	0.019±0.003* (26)	0.064±0.007 ⁼ (90)
	HP	0.092±0.006 (100)	0.040±0.012* (44)	0.020±0.013* (22)	0.085±0.002 ⁼ (93)
	OT	0.071±0.008 (100)	0.028±0.012* (40)	0.019±0.008* (27)	0.063±0.007 ⁼ (90)

⁼, Significant (P<0.05) when student's 't' test was applied between 80% of LC_{50} (96h) and withdrawal groups

Details are as given in Table I.

level was significantly enhanced after the exposure to sub-lethal doses in the studied body tissues. Lactic dehydrogenase (LDH), cytochrome oxidase and acetylcholinesterase (AChE) activities were significantly reduced, while succi-

nic dehydrogenase (SDH) activity was increased after the exposure.

Glycogen level was reduced to 70%, 68% and 64%. Pyruvate level was reduced to 33%, 38% and 31% in muscle, liver and gonadal tissue of fish. Lactate

Table V. Changes in total protein, total free amino acids, nucleic acid (DNA and RNA) (mg/mg) level and activity of protease (μmol of tyrosine equivalents/mg protein/h) and acid and alkaline phosphatase (μmol substrate hydrolysed/30 min/mg protein) in different tissues of freshwater fish *Channa punctatus* after exposure to 96h against 40% and 80% of LC₅₀ (24h) of aqueous latex extracts of *Croton tiglium* and 7th days after withdrawal.

Tabla V. Cambios en los niveles de proteínas totales, ácidos nucleicos (DNA y RNA) (mg/mg) y en la actividad proteasa (μmol de equivalentes de tirosina/mg de proteína/h) y fosfatasas ácida y alcalina (μmol sustrato hidrolizado/30 min/mg proteína) en distintos tejidos del pez *Channa punctatus* tras exposición a LC₅₀ (24h) de extracto acuoso de latex de *Croton tiglium* al 40 y al 80% después de 96 horas y 7 días después de la prueba.

	Tissues	Control	40% of LC ₅₀ (24h) (0.024 mg,DW/L)	80% of LC ₅₀ (24h) (0.048 mg,DW/L)	7 th day after withdrawal
Protein	Muscle	160.1±0.77 (100)	133.5±0.24* (83)	124.6±0.26* (78)	156.8±0.71= (98)
	Liver	141.0±0.69 (100)	119.8±0.24* (85)	105.7±0.24* (75)	136.7±1.00= (97)
	Gonadal	136.6±1.00 (100)	117.4±0.12* (86)	92.8±0.08* (68)	131.1±0.45= (96)
Amino acid	Muscle	28.5±0.24 (100)	30.4±0.29 (107)	33.9±0.40* (119)	29.3±0.23= (103)
	Liver	22.6±0.40 (100)	24.8±0.47 (110)	28.2±0.40* (125)	23.7±0.38= (105)
	Gonadal	20.6±0.78 (100)	28.2±0.02* (137)	29.4±0.02* (143)	21.4±0.10= (104)
DNA	Muscle	142.44±0.75 (100)	123.9±0.16* (87)	102.7±0.14* (72)	136.7±0.69= (96)
	Liver	140.01±0.71 (100)	133.0±0.07 (95)	107.8±0.14* (77)	134.4±0.51= (96)
	Gonadal	145.00±0.75 (100)	117.40±0.45* (81)	107.30±0.26* (74)	137.7±0.34= (95)
RNA	Muscle	103.00±0.28 (100)	84.41±0.03* (82)	69.01±0.04* (67)	99.9±0.28= (97)
	Liver	100.0±0.29 (100)	86.02±0.18* (86)	72.01±0.18* (72)	100.0±0.21= (96)
	Gonadal	106.60±0.61 (100)	85.20±0.43* (80)	74.60±0.28* (70)	98.5±0.17= (93)
Protease	Muscle	0.592±0.011 (100)	0.752±0.147* (127)	0.817±0.018* (138)	0.639±0.061= (108)
	Liver	0.608±0.016 (100)	0.681±0.018* (112)	0.778±0.015* (128)	0.571±0.012= (94)
	Gonadal	0.698±0.017 (100)	0.803±0.015* (115)	0.838±0.016* (120)	0.739±0.154= (106)
Acid phosphatase	Muscle	0.283±0.013 (100)	0.113±0.011* (40)	0.84±0.013* (30)	0.260±0.0123= (92)
	Liver	0.297±0.017 (100)	0.130±0.011* (44)	0.109±0.009* (37)	0.276±0.013= (93)
	Gonadal	0.288±0.015 (100)	0.120±0.007* (42)	0.092±0.017* (32)	0.267±0.012= (93)
Alkaline phosphatase	Muscle	0.434±0.012 (100)	0.177±0.007* (41)	0.164±0.04* (38)	0.394±0.002= (91)
	Liver	0.463±0.005 (100)	0.199±0.008* (43)	0.185±0.007* (40)	0.426±0.003= (92)
	Gonadal	0.438±0.012 (100)	0.175±0.007* (40)	0.162±0.004* (37)	0.403±0.004= (92)

=, Significant (P<0.05) when student's 't' test was applied between 80% of LC₅₀ (24h) and withdrawal groups
Details are as given in Table I.

level was increased to 165%, 172% and 162% of controls after 96h treatment with 80% of LC₅₀ (96h) of aqueous latex extracts in muscle, liver and gonadal tissues of fish, respectively (Table VI).

LDH activity was reduced to 86%, 83% and 84% and activity of cytochrome oxidase was reduced to 75%, 73% and

76%. AChE activity was reduced to 32%, 36% and 32% in muscle, liver and gonadal tissue of fish, respectively. SDH activity was increased to 124%, 126% and 122% of controls after 96h treatment with 80% of LC₅₀ of aqueous latex extracts in muscle, liver and gonadal tissues of fish, respectively (Table VI).

Table VI. Changes in glycogen (mg/g), pyruvate ($\mu\text{mol/g}$), lactate (mg/g) level and activity of LDH ($\mu\text{mol/mg protein/h}$), SDH ($\mu\text{mol of dye reduced/min/mg protein}$), cytochrome oxidase (arbitrary unit/min/mg protein) and AChE ($\mu\text{mol 'SH' hydrolysed/min/mg protein}$) in different tissues of *Channa punctatus* after exposure to 96h against 40% and 80% of LC₅₀ (24h) of aqueous latex extracts of *Croton tiglium* and 7th days after withdrawal.

Tabla IV. Cambios en los niveles de glucógeno (mg/g), piruvato ($\mu\text{mol/g}$), lactato (mg/g), actividades de LDH ($\mu\text{mol/mg proteína/h}$), SDH ($\mu\text{mol de colorante reducido/min/mg proteína}$), citocromo oxidasa (unidad arbitraria/min/mg proteína) y AChE ($\mu\text{mol SH hidrolizado/min/mg proteína}$) en distintos tejidos del pez *Channa punctatus* tras exposición a LC₅₀ (24h) de extracto acuoso de latex de *Croton tiglium* al 40 y al 80% después de 96 horas y 7 días después de la prueba.

	Tissues	Control	40% of LC ₅₀ (24h) (0.024 mg,DW/L)	80% of LC ₅₀ (24h) (0.048 mg,DW/L)	7 th days after withdrawal
Glycogen	Muscle	1.92±0.001 (100)	1.46±0.006* (76)	1.34±0.04* (70)	1.67±0.01 ⁼ (87)
	Liver	1.98±0.002 (100)	1.44±0.003* (73)	1.34±0.04* (68)	1.69±0.03 ⁼ (85)
	Gonadal	1.73±0.01 (100)	1.28±0.03* (74)	1.10±0.02* (64)	1.51±0.03 ⁼ (87)
Pyruvate	Muscle	2.416±0.018 (100)	1.232±0.016* (51)	0.797±0.028* (33)	2.150±0.017 ⁼ (89)
	Liver	3.076±0.018 (100)	1.876±0.036* (61)	1.168±0.008* (38)	2.768±0.035 ⁼ (90)
	Gonadal	2.133±0.036 (100)	1.045±0.017* (49)	0.661±0.023* (31)	1.95±0.016 ⁼ (91)
Lactate	Muscle	2.816±0.018 (100)	3.379±0.092* (120)	4.646±0.064* (165)	3.041±0.082 ⁼ (108)
	Liver	2.233±0.023 (100)	2.925±0.023* (131)	3.840±0.076* (172)	2.500±0.069 ⁼ (112)
	Gonadal	3.816±0.083 (100)	4.502±0.088* (118)	6.181±0.092* (162)	4.159±0.043 ⁼ (109)
LDH	Muscle	431.5±0.88 (100)	392.6±0.84 (91)	371.0±0.85* (86)	392.7±0.83 ⁼ (91)
	Liver	517.0±1.0 (100)	475.6±0.81 (92)	429.1±0.88* (83)	465.3±0.78 ⁼ (90)
	Gonadal	434.2±0.87 (100)	403.8±0.72 (93)	364.2±0.85* (84)	395.1±0.81 ⁼ (91)
SDH	Muscle	49.4±0.21 (100)	56.3±0.21* (114)	61.2±0.27* (124)	53.8±0.21 ⁼ (109)
	Liver	52.6±0.23 (100)	58.9±0.22* (112)	66.2±0.22* (126)	58.3±0.23 ⁼ (111)
	Gonadal	54.4±0.26 (100)	63.1±0.18* (116)	66.3±0.15* (122)	59.2±0.26 ⁼ (107)
Cytochrome oxidase	Muscle	25.92±0.21 (100)	22.03±0.23* (85)	19.44±0.22* (75)	24.36±0.33 ⁼ (94)
	Liver	28.30±0.07 (100)	23.77±0.21* (84)	20.65±0.22* (73)	20.65±0.022 ⁼ (91)
	Gonadal	31.20±0.07 (100)	27.14±0.13* (87)	23.71±0.16* (76)	25.75±0.19 ⁼ (92)
AChE	Muscle	0.093±0.0012 (100)	0.049±0.0006* (53)	0.029±0.0007* (32)	0.083±0.0002 ⁼ (90)
	Liver	0.099±0.0011 (100)	0.054±0.0004* (55)	0.035±0.0003* (36)	0.092±0.0001 ⁼ (92)
	Gonadal	0.095±0.0025 (100)	0.049±0.0008* (52)	0.030±0.0006* (32)	0.087±0.0005 ⁼ (91)

⁼ Significant (P<0.05) when student's 't' test was applied between 80% of LC₅₀ (24h) and withdrawal groups

Details are as given in Table I.

DISCUSSION

It is evident from the results presented here that the aqueous extracts of the latex of *Croton tiglium* besides being potent molluscicides (YADAV AND SINGH, 2001) are toxic to fish *Channa punctatus* at higher concentrations and

longer exposure periods. The exposure to 40% and 80% of snail LC₅₀ for 24h did not caused any significant changes in the level of carbohydrate and nitrogenous metabolism of fish tissues, while this treatment continued up to 96 hours decreased the carbohydrate and nitrogenous metabolism levels significantly.

MOMMENSEN AND WALSH (1992) reported that proteins are mainly involved in the architecture of the cell, which is the chief source of nitrogenous metabolism and during chronic period of stress they are also a source of energy. During stress condition, snails needed more energy to detoxify the toxicants and to overcome stress (ARUNACHALAM, JAYALAKSHAMI AND ABOOKER, 1980). The depletion of protein fraction in nervous, hepatopancreas and ovotestis tissues may have been due to their degradation and possible utilization of degraded products for metabolic purposes. Increment in free amino acids level was the result of breakdown of protein for energy requirement and impaired incorporation of amino acids in protein synthesis, but it also could be attributed to the lesser use of amino acids and their involvement in the maintenance of an acid-base balance. Stress conditions induce the transamination pathway. Inhibition of DNA synthesis might affect both protein as well as amino acid levels by decreasing the level of RNA in protein synthesis machinery (NORDENSKJOLD, SODERHALL AND MOLDEUS, 1979). Euphorbiales are a potential inhibitor of DNA synthesis, which might result in reduction of RNA level and consequently affecting protein synthesis and amino acid levels as showed are results.

The enzyme protease functions in hydrolysing proteins to free amino acids and small peptides. The increase in the protease activity corroborates with the enhancement in the FAA (Free amino acids) level of the three tissues, the formation of which might be the result of protein hydrolysis of the three tissues suggesting stimulation during toxic stress. Similar trend of results on protease activity was also reported by several workers in different animals (*Tilapia mossambica* (Peters), *Pila globosa* (Swaimson) including mammal (MILLWARD, 1970; SIVA PRASADA RAO, 1980; SIVAJIAH, 1980; KABEER, SAHIB, SIVA PRASAD, SAMBASIVA AND RAMANA RAO, 1984). SINGH AND AGARWAL (1992) reported that the latexes of several euphorbious plants

significantly reduced the alkaline and acid phosphatase activity in nervous tissue of *Lymnaea acuminata*. So the reduction in protein level may be due to the inhibition of alkaline phosphatase activity, as it plays an important role in protein synthesis (PILO, ASNANI AND SHAH, 1972) and other secretory activities (IBRAHIM, HIGAZI AND DEMIAN, 1974).

Carbohydrates are the primary and immediate source of energy of the metabolism. ARASTA, BAIS AND THAKUR, (1996) suggested that in stress condition, carbohydrates reserves depleted to meet energy demand, thus depletion of glycogen may be due to direct utilization for energy generation, a demand caused by active moiety-induced hypoxia. Euphorbiales inhibit acetylcholinesterase activity, which results in an increase of acetylcholine contents (SINGH AND AGARWAL, 1984; SINGH AND AGARWAL, 1990, 1991; SINGH *ET AL.*, 1996). Increase level of acetylcholine has been shown to enhance the secretion of catecholamine (NILSSON, ABRAHAMSSON AND GROVE, 1976), which may bring about glycogenolysis. Thus, glycogenolysis seems to be the result of increased secretion of catecholamine due to stress (SINGH AND SRIVASTAVA, 1992; SINGH AND AGARWAL, 1993). Decrease in pyruvate level is due to higher energy demand during exposure, which is suggests the possibility of a shift towards anaerobic dependence due to a remarkable drop in aerobic segment. The decrease in pyruvate could be due to its conversion to lactate, or due to its mobilization to form amino acids, lipids, triglycerides and glycogen synthesis in addition to its role as a detoxification factor (SATHYA PRASAD, 1983). The increase in lactate also suggests a shift towards anaerobiosis as a consequence of hypoxia leading to respiratory distress (DOMSCHE, DOMSCHE AND CLASSEN, 1971; SIVA PRASADA RAO, 1980). Development of such internal hypoxic conditions may be ultimately responsible for the shift to the less efficient anaerobic metabolism, evidenced by the change in lactate content observed during this study.

Lactic dehydrogenase (LDH) forms the centre for a delicately balanced equilibrium between catabolism and anabolism of carbohydrates (EVERSE AND KALPAN, 1973). Lactic dehydrogenase (LDH) catalyze the inter-conversions of lactic acid and pyruvic acid during anaerobic conditions. Inhibition of LDH and cytochrome oxidase activity indicates that latex extracts of *Croton tiglium* significantly inhibits aerobic, as well as anaerobic metabolism in exposed animals. Succinic dehydrogenase (SDH) is one of the active regulatory enzymes of the TCA cycle. The reasons for an increase SDH level after exposure to extracts of latex are not clear. A similar situation was observed by GUPTA and KAPOOR (1975), who reported a increase of SDH level in malathion exposed, irradiated rats.

Cytochrome oxidase is a terminal enzyme of the electron transport chain. Inhibition in cytochrome oxidase activity by plant moieties supports that Euphorbiales show a profound impact on the oxidative metabolism, possibly due to their influence on respiratory process like electron transport system (ETS). Decrease in cytochrome oxidase might be either the result of reduced availability of O₂, which in turns has reduce the capacity of electron transport system to produce ATP molecules or should be due to the direct impact of the active moiety. Anticholinesterase com-

pounds are known to usually inhibit mitochondrial reactions like the function of the cytochrome oxidase in electron transport system. Since Euphorbiales are anticholinesterase inhibitor, they disrupt Krebs' cycle by diminishing the rate of electron transport system and oxidative phosphorylation, resulting in less synthesis of ATP.

Withdrawal experiments were performed to see whether biochemical alteration by exposure to plant moiety would return normal, if the treatment were discontinued. There was nearly complete recovery of total protein, total free amino acid, lactate, nucleic acid (DNA and RNA), pyruvate level and in the activity of cytochrome oxidase, SDH, protease, LDH, AChE and acid and alkaline phosphatase and a partial recovery of glycogen level in the different body tissues of snail and fish (Table II, IV, V and VI).

We therefore believe that these plant extracts may eventually be of great value for the control of aquatic non-target organisms.

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